

On NCT- Set Theory

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Abstract: We introduce a new class of neutrosophic crisp set, and then it presented some operations via this sets like, NCT –intersection, NCT –union and algebraic NCT –difference to arrive at the algebraic ring construction. Also, we introduce the NCT – points, which showed that a NCT –set is NCT –union of its NCT –points, and so did we introduced the concept of the function on this sets, called NCT – function and some of their important properties. Finally, we introduced the concept of the topology and some of the concepts entrusted to it, as an introduction to those spaces that can be studied in detail in the future.

Keywords: NCT – sets; NCT –points; NCT –function and NCT –topological spaces.

1. Introduction

The main focus of this research is the construction of a new type of neutrosophic crisp sets, and the first to know these sets neutrosophic and neutrosophic crisp sets is the scientist Florentin between the years 1999-2005 [1-3], when we looking at these sets, we notice that they are determined within spaces $X \times [0, 1]^3$ and $P(X) \times P(X) \times P(X)$, respectively when Zadeh [4] defined the fuzzy sets in 1965, which were identified in space $X \times [0, 1]$, and through this, Salama and Florentin generalized these sets, which he called neutrosophic sets [5-7]. The researcher Almohammed [8] invested in the fuzzy sets by finding a new definition of the local function in 2020. Imran et al. [9-11] provided the view of new types of weakly neutrosophic crisp continuity, new concepts of weakly neutrosophic crisp separation axioms, and new concepts of neutrosophic crisp open sets. Molodtsov [12] found a new type of sets at the $E \times P(X)$ (where X is universal set and E the parameters of elements of X) spaces and named them soft sets, where Al-Swidi and others [13-16] invested these sets by linking them with the fuzzy sets as well as defining new points, which in turn obtained equivalents for the separation axioms. Tomma et al. [17-19] gave the view of stable neutrosophic crisp topological space, necessary and sufficient conditions for a stability of the concepts of stable interior and stable exterior via neutrosophic crisp sets, and confused crisp set stable neutrosophic topological spaces. Al-Tamimi et al. [20] provided partner sets for generalizations of multi neutrosophic sets. Sfook et al. [21] introduced neutrosophic crisp grill topological spaces. Abdulsada et al. [22,23] provided the view of separation axioms of center topological space, and Center set theory of proximity space. Finally, the senses of new types of weakly neutrosophic crisp open mappings and new types of weakly neutrosophic crisp closed functions were informed by Al-Obaidi et al. [24,25]. In this research, we introduce a new concept of neutrosophic crisp set, and then it presented some operations via this sets like, NCT –intersection, NCT –union and algebraic

NCT –difference to arrive at the algebraic ring construction. Also, we introduce the **NCT** – points, which showed that a **NCT** –set is **NCT** –union of its **NCT** –points, and so did we introduced the class of the function on this sets, called **NCT** – function and some of their important properties.

2. NCT- Sets

We presented a new class of neutrosophic crisp sets, complete with a neutrosophic crisp point, all operations are binary, a ring-building qualification, and boolean algebra.

Definition 2.1. Let $X \neq \emptyset$. A neutrosophic crisp triple set NCT_A is an object having the form $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$. Where $A_1, A_2, A_3 \subseteq X$ satisfying $A_1 \subseteq A_2$ and $A_2 \cap A_3 = \emptyset$. And $NCT(X) = \{NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle : A_1 \subseteq A_2 \text{ and } A_2 \cap A_3 = \emptyset\}$ is the collection of all **NCT** – sets on X . From this definition we see that if $A_3 = X$, then $A_1 = A_2 = \emptyset$ and if $A_2 = X$, then $A_3 = \emptyset$, finally if $A_1 = X$, then $A_2 = X$ and $A_3 = \emptyset$.

Definition 2.2. Let $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ and $NCT_B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ are **NCT** –a non-empty set X over sets. Therefore:

1. NCT_A is a **NCT** – subset of NCT_B if $A_3 \supseteq B_3$ and $A_1 \subseteq B_1, A_2 \subseteq B_2$. We write $NCT_A \subseteq NCT_B$.
2. $NCT_A = NCT_B$ iff $NCT_A \subseteq NCT_B$ and $NCT_B \subseteq NCT_A$.
3. The **NCT** –complement of **NCT** – set NCT_A is $CNCT_A = \langle A_3, A_2^c, A_1 \rangle$.
4. $NCT_A \sqcup NCT_B = \langle A_1 \cup B_1, A_2 \cup B_2, A_3 \cap B_3 \rangle$ is a crisp triple set that is neutrosophic in union (**NCT** –union set).
5. $NCT_A \cap NCT_B = \langle A_1 \cap B_1, A_2 \cap B_2, A_3 \cup B_3 \rangle$ is the intersection a crisp triple set that is neutrosophic (**NCT** –intersection sets).
6. $NCT_A - NCT_B = NCT_A \cap CNCT_B$.
7. $NCT_A \triangle NCT_B = (NCT_A \cap CNCT_B) \sqcup (CNCT_A \cap NCT_B)$.

Now we will explain the concepts **NCT** –universal and **NCT** –null set which are among the basic concepts in our work.

Definition 2.3. Let $X \neq \emptyset$. Then:

1. $NCT_X = \langle X, X, \emptyset \rangle$ is **NCT** –universal set.
2. $NCT_\emptyset = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, X \rangle$ is **NCT** –null set. Clearly $CNCT_X = NCT_\emptyset$ and $CNCT_\emptyset = NCT_X$.

The three most significant relationships **NCT** –union, **NCT** –intersection and **NCT** –complement listed in the following properties.

Proposition 2.4. Let $NCT_S = \langle S_1, S_2, S_3 \rangle$ and $NCT_J = \langle J_1, J_2, J_3 \rangle$ are **NCT** – a nonempty set X over sets. Then:

1. $NCT_S \cap NCT_S = NCT_S$.
2. $NCT_S \sqcup NCT_\emptyset = NCT_S$.
3. $NCT_S \sqcup NCT_X = NCT_X$.
4. $NCT_S \cap NCT_\emptyset = NCT_\emptyset$.
5. $C(NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J) = CNCT_S \cap CNCT_J$.
6. $C(NCT_S \cap NCT_J) = CNCT_S \sqcup CNCT_J$.
7. $NCT_S \sqcup NCT_S = NCT_S$.

Proving the above proposition directly by applying Definitions 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3.

For any $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, we get the following two properties, but the opposite is not necessarily true $NCT_\emptyset \subseteq NCT_A \cap CNCT_A$ and $NCT_A \sqcup CNCT_A \subseteq NCT_X$ if $X = \{q_1, q_2, q_3\}$ and $NCT_A =$

$\langle \{q_1\}, \{q_1, q_2\}, \{q_3\} \rangle$, then $NCT_A \cap CNCT_A = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{q_1, q_3\} \rangle \not\subseteq NCT_\emptyset = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, X \rangle$. And, if $X = \{q_1, q_2, q_3\}$ and $NCT_A = \langle \{q_1\}, \{q_1, q_2\}, \{q_3\} \rangle$, then $NCT_X = \langle X, X, \emptyset \rangle \not\subseteq (NCT_A \sqcup CNCT_A) = \langle \{q_1, q_3\}, X, \emptyset \rangle$.

The following proposition shows the algebraic properties (associative and distributive laws) of these NCT – sets via NCT – union and NCT –intersection relations.

Proposition 2.5. Let $NCT_O = \langle O_1, O_2, O_3 \rangle$, $NCT_Q = \langle Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 \rangle$ and $NCT_J = \langle J_1, J_2, J_3 \rangle$ over a nonempty set X , be three NCT –sets. Then:

1. $NCT_O \cap (NCT_Q \sqcup NCT_J) = (NCT_O \cap NCT_Q) \sqcup (NCT_O \cap NCT_J)$.
2. $NCT_O \cap (NCT_Q \cap NCT_J) = (NCT_O \cap NCT_Q) \cap NCT_J$.
3. $NCT_O \sqcup (NCT_Q \sqcup NCT_J) = (NCT_O \sqcup NCT_Q) \sqcup NCT_J$.
4. $NCT_O \sqcup (NCT_Q \cap NCT_J) = (NCT_O \sqcup NCT_Q) \cap (NCT_O \sqcup NCT_J)$.

Now we defined the NCT –union and NCT –intersection relations on any collection of NCT –sets.

Definition 2.6. Let $\{NCT_{A_i} : i \in I\}$ be a NCT –sets in X , and $NCT_{A_i} = \langle A_{i1}, A_{i2}, A_{i3} \rangle$. Then

1. $\sqcup_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i} = \langle \cup_{i \in I} A_{i1}, \cup_{i \in I} A_{i2}, \cap_{i \in I} A_{i3} \rangle$.
2. $\cap_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i} = \langle \cap_{i \in I} A_{i1}, \cap_{i \in I} A_{i2}, \cup_{i \in I} A_{i3} \rangle$.

Proposition 2.7. Let NCT_A, NCT_B, NCT_C and $\{NCT_{A_i} : i \in I\}$ in X . Then

1. $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$ and $NCT_B \sqsubseteq NCT_C$, implies $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_C$.
2. $NCT_{A_i} \sqsubseteq NCT_B \quad \forall i \in I$, then $\sqcup_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i} \sqsubseteq NCT_B$.
3. $NCT_B \sqsubseteq NCT_{A_i} \quad \forall i \in I$, then $NCT_B \sqsubseteq \cap_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$.
4. $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$ iff $CNCT_B \sqsubseteq CNCT_A$.

Proof: Obvious.

Now we present the definition of points NCT –points.

Definition 2.8. Let $X \neq \emptyset$ and $p \in X$. So NCT –points ($NCTP$) are structure:

1. $NCT_{\bar{p}} = \langle \{p\}, \{p\}, \{p\}^c \rangle$.
2. $NCT_{\tilde{p}} = \langle \emptyset, \{p\}, \{p\}^c \rangle$.
3. $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{p\}^c \rangle$.

It's simple to see that NCT –points are NCT –sets. Also, the cardinal number of all NCT –points is $3n$, where n is the cardinal number of universal sets X .

Definition 2.9. Let $X \neq \emptyset$ and $p \in X$ and $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$. Then the NCT –belong as follows:

1. $NCT_{\bar{p}} \in NCT_A$ iff $p \in A_1$ and $NCT_{\bar{p}} \notin NCT$ iff $p \notin A_1$.
2. $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A$ iff $p \in A_2$ and $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \notin NCT$ iff $p \notin A_2$.
3. $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \in NCT_A$ iff $p \notin A_3$ and $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \notin NCT$ iff $p \in A_3$.

We now take the properties of belonging to the three points.

Proposition 2.10. Let $\{NCT_{A_i} : i \in I\}$ is NCT –set in X . Then

1. $NCT_{\bar{p}} \in \cap_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $NCT_{\bar{p}} \in NCT_{A_i}$ for each $i \in I$.
2. $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in \cap_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_{A_i}$ for each $i \in I$.
3. $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \in \cap_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \in NCT_{A_i}$ for each $i \in I$.
4. $NCT_{\bar{p}} \in \sqcup_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $\exists i \in I$ such that $NCT_{\bar{p}} \in NCT_{A_i}$.
5. $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in \sqcup_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $\exists i \in I$ such that $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_{A_i}$.
6. $NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \in \sqcup_{i \in I} NCT_{A_i}$ iff $\exists i \in I \ni NCT_{\tilde{\tilde{p}}} \in NCT_{A_i}$.

Proposition 2.11. Let NCT_A and NCT_B is NCT –set in X . Then:

- i. $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$ iff $\forall NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ with $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Rightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$, for each $NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ with $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Rightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$ and for each $NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ we have $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Rightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$.
- ii. $NCT_A = NCT_B$ iff for each $NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ we have $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Leftrightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$ and for each $NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ we have $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Leftrightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$ and for each $NCT_{\tilde{p}}$ we have $NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A \Leftrightarrow NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_B$.

Proposition 2.12. Let $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ be triple in X . Then $NCT_A = (\{NCT_{\tilde{p}} : NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A\}) \sqcup (\{NCT_{\tilde{p}} : NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A\}) \sqcup (\{NCT_{\tilde{p}} : NCT_{\tilde{p}} \in NCT_A\})$.

Proposition 2.13. Let $NCT_S = \langle S_1, S_2, S_3 \rangle$, $NCT_J = \langle J_1, J_2, J_3 \rangle$ and $NCT_R = \langle R_1, R_2, R_3 \rangle$ be NCT -sets. Then:

1. $NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J \supseteq (NCT_S \cap NCT_J) \sqcup (NCT_J - NCT_S) \sqcup (NCT_S - NCT_J)$.
2. $(NCT_S - NCT_J) \sqcup (NCT_S - NCT_R) = NCT_S - (NCT_J \cap NCT_R)$.
3. $(NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J) - (NCT_R - NCT_S) = NCT_S \sqcup (NCT_J - NCT_R)$.
4. $(NCT_S \cap NCT_J) - (CNCT_S \sqcup NCT_R) = NCT_S \cap (NCT_J - NCT_R)$.
5. Not necessary if $NCT_S \sqsubseteq NCT_J$ and $NCT_S \sqsubseteq CNCT_J$, then $NCT_S = NCT_{\varphi}$.
6. Not necessary if $NCT_S \sqsubseteq NCT_J$ and $CNCT_S \sqsubseteq NCT_J$, then $NCT_S = NCT_X$.
7. $(NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J) - NCT_J \supseteq NCT_S - NCT_J$.
8. $NCT_S - NCT_J \sqsubseteq NCT_S - (NCT_S \cap NCT_J)$.
9. $\cap \{NCT_J \in NCT_S(X)\} = NCT_{\varphi}$.
10. $NCT_S \cap CNCT_J \sqsubseteq (NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J) \cap CNCT_J$.
11. $(NCT_S \sqcup NCT_J) - (NCT_J \cap NCT_S) \supseteq (NCT_S - NCT_J) \sqcup (NCT_J - NCT_S)$.
12. $NCT_S - (NCT_J \sqcup NCT_R) = (NCT_S - NCT_J) - NCT_R$.
13. $NCT_S \triangle NCT_{\varphi} = NCT_S$.
14. $NCT_{\varphi} = NCT_S \triangle NCT_S$ if and only if $S_1 \cup S_3 = X$.
15. $NCT_S \triangle NCT_J = NCT_J \triangle NCT_S$.

Proof.

The converse of part (1) is not true in general for example, if $X = \{o_1, o_2, o_3\}$, $NCT_A = \{\{o_1\}, \{o_1, o_2\}, \{o_3\}\}$ and $NCT_B = \{\{o_2\}, \{o_2, o_3\}, \{o_1\}\}$, then: $NCT_A - (NCT_A \cap NCT_B) = \{\{o_1\}, \{o_1\}, \{o_3\}\} \not\subseteq NCT_A - NCT_B = \{\{o_1\}, \{o_1\}, \{o_2, o_3\}\}$.

The converse of part 2 is not true generally, for instance, if $X = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$, $NCT_A = \{\{e_1\}, \{e_1, e_2\}, \{e_3\}\}$ and $NCT_B = \{\{o_2\}, \{o_2, o_3\}, \{o_1\}\}$, then: $NCT_A \sqcup NCT_B = \{\{o_1, o_2\}, X, \emptyset\} \not\subseteq (NCT_A \cap NCT_B) \sqcup (NCT_B - NCT_A) \sqcup (NCT_A - NCT_B) = \{\{o_1\}, \{o_1, o_3\}, \emptyset\}$.

Part 7, Let $X = \{o_1, o_2, o_3\}$, $NCT_A = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{o_1, o_2\} \rangle$ and $NCT_B = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{o_1\} \rangle$, then $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$, $NCT_A \sqsubseteq CNCT_B$ and $NCT_A \neq NCT_{\varphi}$.

Part 8, Let $X = \{o_1, o_2, o_3\}$, $NCT_A = \langle X, X, \{o_1, o_2\} \rangle$ and $NCT_B = \langle X, X, \{o_1\} \rangle$, then $NCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$, $CNCT_A \sqsubseteq NCT_B$ and $NCT_A \neq NCT_X$.

Since Proposition 2.13, part 12 assures that the NCT -null set serves as an identification element for Proposition 13.2, part 13 ensures that every member of $NC^*(X) = \{NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle : NCT_A \text{ is } NCT\text{-set and } A_1 \cup A_3 = X\}$.

Finally, the fact that part 14 has its own inverse demonstrates that the symbol is commutative. All of this lends credence to the contention that $(NC^*(X), \triangle)$ is a commutative group.

Theorem 2.14. Let X is non-null and $NC^*(X) = \{NCT_S = \langle S_1, S_2, S_3 \rangle : NCT_A \text{ is } NCT\text{-set and } S_1 \cup S_3 = X\}$ on X . So $(NC^*(X), \triangle, \cap)$ form a ring.

Proof.

According to propositions 2.4 and propositions 2.5, the groups $(NC^*(X), \cap)$ and $(NC^*(X), \Delta)$ are semigroups and commutative groups. Only the distribution on the left must be examined \cap operation on Δ .

$(NCT_S \cap NCT_W) \Delta (NCT_S \cap NCT_P) = \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_W) \cap (CNCT_S \sqcup CNCT_P)\} \sqcup \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_P) \cap (CNCT_S \sqcup CNCT_W)\} = \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_W) \cap CNCT_S\} \sqcup \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_W) \cap CNCT_P\} \sqcup \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_P) \cap CNCT_S\} \sqcup \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_P) \cap CNCT_W\} = \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_W) \cap CNCT_P\} \sqcup \{(NCT_S \cap NCT_P) \cap CNCT_W\} = NCT_S \cap (NCT_W \Delta NCT_P)$. Therefore $(NC^*(X), \cap, \Delta)$ is a ring.

Now we introduce the concept of *NCT*-function.

Definition 2.15. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Define *NCT* –function $f_{NCT} : NCT(X) \rightarrow NCT(Y)$ by:

1. If $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle \in NCT_A(X)$, then $f_{NCT}(NCT_A) = \langle f(A_1), f(A_2), f - (A_3) \rangle$, where $f - (A_3) = Y - (f(X - A_3))$.
2. If $NCT_B = \langle R_1, R_2, R_3 \rangle \in NCT_B(Y)$, then $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_B) = \langle f^{-1}(R_1), f^{-1}(R_2), f^{-1}(R_3) \rangle$.

We now take the most important properties of the *NCT*-function that we will adopt in our research.

Proposition 2.16. Let $f_{NCT} : NCT(X) \rightarrow NCT(Y)$ be a *NCT* – function and $NCT_{A_i}, NCT_{A_i} (i \in I) \in NCT(X), NCT_{B_j}, NCT_{B_j} (j \in J) \in NCT(Y)$. Then:

1. $NCT_{A_1} \sqsubseteq NCT_{A_2} \Rightarrow f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_1}) \sqsubseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_2})$.
2. $NCT_{B_1} \sqsubseteq NCT_{B_2} \Rightarrow f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_{B_1}) \sqsubseteq f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_{B_2})$.
3. If $NCT_A \sqsubseteq f_{NCT}^{-1}(f_{NCT}(NCT_A))$ and f is 1-1, then $NCT_A = f_{NCT}^{-1}(f_{NCT}(NCT_A))$.
4. If $f_{NCT}(f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_B)) \sqsubseteq NCT_B$ and f is onto, then $f_{NCT}(f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_B)) = NCT_B$.
5. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(\sqcup NCT_{B_j}) = \sqcup f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_{B_j})$.
6. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(\cap NCT_{B_j}) = \cap f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_{B_j})$.
7. $f_{NCT}(\sqcup NCT_{A_i}) = \sqcup f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_i})$.
8. $f_{NCT}(\cap NCT_{A_i}) \sqsubseteq (\cap f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_i}))$ and if f is 1-1, then $f_{NCT}(\cap NCT_{A_i}) = \cap f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_i})$.
9. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_Y) = NCT_X$.
10. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_\emptyset) = NCT_\emptyset$.
11. $f_{NCT}(NCT_X) = NCT_Y$, if f is onto.
12. $f_{NCT}(NCT_\emptyset) = NCT_\emptyset$.

Proof.

Let $NCT_{A_i} = \langle A_{i1}, A_{i2}, A_{i3} \rangle, NCT_{B_j} = \langle B_{j1}, B_{j2}, B_{j3} \rangle, (i \in I, j \in J)$, $NCT_A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ and $NCT_B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$.

1. Let $NCT_{A_1} \sqsubseteq NCT_{A_2}$. Since $A_{11} \sqsubseteq A_{21}, A_{12} \sqsubseteq A_{22}$ and $A_{23} \sqsubseteq A_{13}$, then $f(A_{11}) \sqsubseteq f(A_{21}), f(A_{12}) \sqsubseteq f(A_{22})$ and $X - A_{13} \sqsubseteq X - A_{23} \Rightarrow f(X - A_{13}) \sqsubseteq f(X - A_{23}) \Rightarrow Y - f(X - A_{23}) \sqsubseteq Y - f(X - A_{13}) \Rightarrow f - (A_{23}) \sqsubseteq f - (A_{13})$. Hence $f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_1}) \sqsubseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_{A_2})$.
2. It is similar to (1).
3. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(f_{NCT}(NCT_A)) = f_{NCT}^{-1}(f_{NCT}(\langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle)) = f_{NCT}^{-1}(\langle f(A_1), f(A_2), f - (A_3) \rangle) = \langle f^{-1}(f(A_1)), f^{-1}(f(A_2)), f^{-1}(f - (A_3)) \rangle \supseteq \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle = NCT_A$.
4. It is similar to (3).
5. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(\sqcup NCT_{B_j}) = f_{NCT}^{-1}(\langle \cup B_{j1}, \cup B_{j2}, \cap B_{j3} \rangle) = \langle f^{-1}(\cup B_{j1}), f^{-1}(\cup B_{j2}), f^{-1}(\cap B_{j3}) \rangle = \langle \cup f^{-1}(B_{j1}), \cup f^{-1}(B_{j2}), \cap f^{-1}(B_{j3}) \rangle = \sqcup f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_{B_j})$.
6. It is similar to (5).

7. $f_{NCT}(\sqcup NCT_{A_i}) = f_{NCT}(\langle \cup A_{i1}, \cup A_{i2}, \cap A_{i3} \rangle) = \langle f(\cup A_{i1}), f(\cup A_{i2}), f - (\cap A_{i3}) \rangle = \langle \cup f(A_{i1}), \cup f(A_{i2}), \cap f - (A_{i3}) \rangle = \sqcup F(NCT_{A_i})$. Notices that $f - (\cap A_{i3}) = Y - f(X - \cap A_{i3}) = Y - f(\cap (X - A_{i3})) = Y - \cap f(X - A_{i3}) = \cap (Y - f(X - A_{i3})) = \cap f - (A_{i3})$.
 8. $f_{NCT}(\cap NCT_{A_i}) = f_{NCT}(\langle \cap A_{i1}, \cap A_{i2}, \cup A_{i3} \rangle) = \langle f(\cap A_{i1}), f(\cap A_{i2}), f - (\cup A_{i3}) \rangle \subseteq \langle \cap f(A_{i1}), \cap f(A_{i2}), \cup f - (A_{i3}) \rangle = \cap F(NCT_{A_i})$. Notices that $f - (\cup A_{i3}) = Y - f(X - \cup A_{i3}) = Y - f(\cup (X - A_{i3})) = Y - \cup f(X - A_{i3}) = \cup (Y - f(X - A_{i3})) = \cup f - (A_{i3})$.
 9. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_Y) = f_{NCT}^{-1}(\langle Y, Y, \emptyset \rangle) = \langle f^{-1}(Y), f^{-1}(Y), f^{-1}(\emptyset) \rangle = \langle X, X, \emptyset \rangle = NCT_X$.
- (10.), (11.), (12.) are like (9.).

3. Neutrosophic Crisp Triple Topological Space

In this section, we investigate some of the properties generated by NCT -sets, such as interior, exterior and boundary NCT - points, which are the structure for all topological concepts, as well as closures.

Definition 3.1. The pair (NCT_X, τ_{NCT}^X) is called neutrosophic crisp triple topological space ($NCTT$) over $NCT(X)$, if you achieve the following:

1. $NCT_X, NCT_\emptyset \in \tau_{NCT}^X$ (\in is the classical belonging).
2. τ_{NCT}^X is closed under the finite NCT -intersection.
3. τ_{NCT}^X is closed under the NCT -union of every subfamily of τ_{NCT}^X .

Any member of τ_{NCT}^X is called NCT -open and the complement is called NCT -closed.

- i- For any NCT - set NCT_A the NCT - interior of NCT_A is of the form $NCT - \text{int}(NCT_A) = \sqcup \{ NCT_P ; \exists NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X \ni NCT_P \in NCT_H \subseteq NCT_A \}$. From this definition we can show that $NCT - \text{int}(NCT_A) = \sqcup \{ NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X ; NCT_H \subseteq NCT_A \}$.
- $NCT_A \in \tau_{NCT}^X$ iff $NCT - \text{int}(NCT_A) = NCT_A$.
- ii- For any NCT -set NCT_A the NCT -closure of NCT_A is of the form $NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A) = \sqcup \{ NCT_P ; \forall NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X \ni NCT_P \in NCT_H \ni NCT_A \cap NCT_H \neq NCT_\emptyset \}$.
- From above we can show that $NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A) = \cap \{ NCT_F ; CNCT_F \in \tau_{NCT}^X \ni NCT_A \subseteq NCT_F \}$.
- NCT_F is NCT -closed iff $NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_F) = NCT_F$.
- iii- For any NCT -set NCT_A the NCT -exterior of NCT_A is of the form $NCT - \text{ext}(NCT_A) = NCT - \text{int}(CNCT_A)$.
- iv- For any NCT -set NCT_A the NCT - boundary of NCT_A is of the form $NCT - \text{fr}(NCT_A) = \sqcup \{ NCT_P ; NCT_P \text{ not } NCT - \text{interior and } NCT - \text{exterior point of } NCT - A \}$.

So, from definition and properties above we can concluded.

- 1- $NCT_X = NCT - \text{int}(NCT_A) \sqcup NCT - \text{ext}(NCT_A) \sqcup NCT - \text{fr}(NCT_A)$, for any NCT -set NCT_A .
- 2- $NCT - \text{int}(NCT_A) = C(NCT - \text{cl}(CNCT_A))$ and $NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A) = C(NCT - \text{int}(CNCT_A))$.

Lemma 3.2. If NCT_H is NCT - open set and any NCT -set NCT_A , then $NCT_H \cap NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A) \subseteq NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A \cap NCT_H)$.

Proof.

Let $NCT_P \in NCT_H \cap NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A)$, if possible, that $NCT_P \notin NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A \cap NCT_H)$. Then there is some NCT - open set NCT_K containing NCT_P and $NCT_K \cap NCT_A \cap NCT_H = NCT_\emptyset$, but $NCT_K \cap NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X$ and $NCT_P \in NCT_K \cap NCT_H$, this shows that $NCT_P \notin NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A)$, which contradiction. This obligates us to $NCT_P \in NCT - \text{cl}(NCT_A \cap NCT_H)$.

Proposition 3.3. Let (NCT_X, τ_{NCT}^X) be any $NCTT$ over $NCT(X)$, then the following properties are hold:

- 1- If $NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X$ or $NCT_K \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, then $NCT - int (NCT - cl(NCT_K \sqcap NCT_H)) = NCT - int(NCT - cl (NCT_K)) \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H))$.
- 2- $NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_A)))) = NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_A))$.
- 3- $NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT_A)))) = NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT_A))$.
- 4- $NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT_A \sqcap NCT_B))) = NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT_A))) \sqcap NCT - int (NCT - cl(NCT - int (NCT_B)))$.
- 5- $NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_A \sqcup NCT_B))) = NCT - cl (NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_A))) \sqcup NCT - cl(NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_B)))$.

Proof.

(1) Since $NCT_H \sqsubseteq NCT - cl(NCT_H)$ and $NCT_K \sqsubseteq NCT - cl(NCT_K)$. So, $NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_K \sqcap NCT_H)) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl (NCT_K) \sqcap NCT - cl(NCT_H)) = NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_K)) \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H))$. Conversely, If $NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X$ or $NCT_K \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, then by Lemma 3.2. For if $NCT_H \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, $NCT_H \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl (NCT_H \sqcap NCT_K))$. (1)

ImPLY that $NCT - int (NCT - cl (NCT_H \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)))) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT - int(NCT - cl (NCT_H \sqcap NCT_K))))$. (2)

But $NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)) \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, again, by Lemma 3.2, we get that $NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H)) \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)) = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H)) \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl[NCT_H \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K))])$. (3)

From eq. (2) and (3), we get the following inequality $NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H)) \sqcap NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_K)) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H \sqcap NCT_K))))$. (4)

But $NCT - int (NCT - cl(NCT - int (NCT - cl(NCT_H \sqcap NCT_K)))) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H \sqcap NCT_K))$. (5)

From eq. (3) and (4) we get the result.

(2) Let $NCT_H = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_A))$, to show that $NCT_H = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H))$. Since $NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H)) = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_A)))) \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT - cl(NCT_A))) = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_A)) = NCT_H$. (6)

But $NCT - int(NCT_H) = NCT - int(NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_A))) = NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_A)) = NCT_H \sqsubseteq NCT - int(NCT - cl(NCT_H))$. (7)

From eq. (6) and (7) we get the result. Similarly, we can prove part (3). To proof 4 and 5, direct from part (1).

Definition 3.4. $NCT -$ function $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ is $NCT -$ open ($NCT -$ closed) map, if the image of each set $NCT -$ open ($NCT -$ closed) in NCT_X is $NCT -$ open ($NCT -$ closed) in NCT_Y .

Example 3.5. let $X = \{1, 2, 3\}, Y = \{a, b, c\}$ and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ s.t. $f(1) = a, f(2) = c$ and $f(3) = b$. For $\tau_{NCT}^X = \{NCT_X, NCT_\phi, \langle \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{3\} \rangle\}$, $\tau_{NCT}^Y = \{NCT_Y, NCT_\phi, \langle \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \phi \rangle\}$, then $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ is not $NCT -$ open and not $NCT -$ closed. For $\tau_{NCT}^X = \{NCT_X, NCT_\phi, \langle \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{3\} \rangle\}$, $\tau_{NCT}^Y = \{NCT_Y, NCT_\phi, \langle \{b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b\} \rangle\}$, then $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ is $NCT -$ open and $NCT -$ closed.

Theorem 3.6. let $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ is $NCT -$ closed ($NCT -$ open) map, for any $NCT_S \sqsubseteq NCT_Y$ and any $NCT -$ open ($NCT -$ closed) NCT_U containing $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_S)$, $\exists NCT -$ open ($NCT -$ closed) NCT_V containing NCT_S s.t. $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_V) \sqsubseteq NCT_U$.

Proof.

Let $NCT_V = NCT_Y - f_{NCT}(NCT_X - NCT_U)$, since $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_S) \subseteq NCT_U$, it follows that $NCT_S \subseteq NCT_V$, and because f_{NCT} is NCT -closed map, NCT_V NCT -open in NCT_Y . Observing that $f_{NCT}^{-1}(NCT_V) = NCT_X - f_{NCT}^{-1}(f_{NCT}(NCT_X - NCT_U)) \subseteq NCT_X - (NCT_X - NCT_U) = NCT_U$.

Theorem 3.7. The following four properties of NCT -function $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ are equivalent:

- i-** f_{NCT} is an NCT -open map.
- ii-** $f_{NCT}(NCT - int(NCT_A)) \subseteq NCT - int(f_{NCT}(NCT_A))$ for each NCT_A in NCT_X .
- iii-** For each NCT -point NCT_P and NCT -open NCT_U containing it, there exist NCT_V NCT -open in NCT_Y containing $f_{NCT}(NCT_P)$ s.t. $NCT_V \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_U)$.

Proof.

Since $NCT - int(NCT_A) \subseteq NCT_A$, by Proposition 2.16 (1), we have $f_{NCT}(NCT - int(NCT_A)) \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_A)$, by (i) $f_{NCT}(NCT - int(NCT_A))$ is NCT -open in NCT_Y and because $NCT - int(f_{NCT}(NCT_A))$ is the NCT -union of NCT -open sets contained in $f_{NCT}(NCT_A)$. We must have $f_{NCT}(NCT - int(NCT_A)) \subseteq NCT - int(f_{NCT}(NCT_A))$.

ii \rightarrow **i**, let NCT_U is NCT -open in NCT_X , $NCT_U = NCT - int(NCT_U)$ and so $f_{NCT}(NCT_U) = f_{NCT}(NCT - int(NCT_U)) \subseteq NCT - int(f_{NCT}(NCT_U)) \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_U)$, thus $f_{NCT}(NCT_U) = NCT - int(f_{NCT}(NCT_U))$ and therefore $f_{NCT}(NCT_U)$ is NCT -open in NCT_Y , that is f_{NCT} is an NCT -open map.

i \rightarrow **iii**, let $NCT_P^X \in NCT_U \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, but $f_{NCT}(NCT_P^X) \in f_{NCT}(NCT_U) \in \tau_{NCT}^Y$.

iii \rightarrow **i**, let $NCT_U \in \tau_{NCT}^X$, by iii, each $NCT_P^Y \in f_{NCT}(NCT_U)$ has NCT -open NCT_V in NCT_Y s.t. $NCT_V \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT_U) = \sqcup \{NCT_V; NCT_P^Y \in f_{NCT}(NCT_U)\}$ is NCT -open in NCT_Y .

Proposition 3.8. $f_{NCT}: (NCT_X, \tau_{NCT}^X) \rightarrow (NCT_Y, \tau_{NCT}^Y)$ is NCT -closed map iff $NCT - cl(f_{NCT}(NCT_A)) \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A))$, for each NCT_A in NCT_X .

Proof.

Since $NCT - cl(NCT_A)$ is NCT -closed in NCT_X , and so $f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A))$ is NCT -closed in NCT_Y , since $f_{NCT}(NCT_A) \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A))$, obtain $NCT - cl(f_{NCT}(NCT_A)) \subseteq NCT - cl(f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A))) = f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A))$. Conversely, if the condition hold and NCT_A is NCT -closed in NCT_X , then $f_{NCT}(NCT_A) \subseteq NCT - cl(f_{NCT}(NCT_A)) \subseteq f_{NCT}(NCT - cl(NCT_A)) = f_{NCT}(NCT_A)$, so that $f_{NCT}(NCT_A)$ is NCT -closed in NCT_Y .

4. Conclusions

First, Salama and Florentin have established several types of neutrosophic crisp points, but they do not cover spaces, the reason for this is the type of neutrosophic crisp space structure with its unique characteristics to be used for life's problems and scientific problems, and then we proposed four new types of neutrosophic crisp points to enhance these spaces as follows:

- 1- New conceptual from the NCP points as $P_{N_1} = \langle P_1, P_2, P_3 \rangle \ni P_i \neq \emptyset$ for $i = 1$ or $i = 2$ or $i = 3$ moreover, there are different focus points empty.
- 2- $P_{N_2} = \langle P_1, P_2, P_3 \rangle \ni P_i \neq \emptyset$ for $i = 1$ or $i = 2$ or $i = 3$ and other points are individual, and $p_i \subseteq A_i, \forall i = 1, 2, 3$ iff $P_{N_i} \in A$.
- 3- $PN_3 = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ is called neutrosophic crisp point, if exactly only one subset $A_i \neq \emptyset$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$.
- 4- $A_i = \emptyset$ for $i = 1$ or $i = 2$ or $i = 3$ and as for the remaining two sets, the first set is any mono set and the second is its complement.

Second, we can modify most of the important mathematical concepts on NCT -sets to be inputs for future research studies, and here we define the concept of ideal and filter as follows.

I- The sub collection I_{NCT} of $T(X)$ is neutrosophic crisp triple ideal (NCT -ideal) if fulfill that:

1. If $NCT_A \in I_{NCT}$ and $NCT_B \subseteq NCT_A$, so $NCT_B \in I_{NCT}$.
2. In general, I_{NCT} is closed beneath the finite NCT – union. In general, 2 using this definition, we are able to alter all notions, namely the results and then in the publications.

II- The sub collection F_{NCT} of $T(X)$ is neutrosophic crisp triple filter (NCT –filter) if:

1. If $NCT_A \in F_{NCT}$ and $NCT_A \subseteq NCT_B$, so $NCT_B \in F_{NCT}$.
2. F_{NCT} is closed under finite NCT –intersection, additionally characterize the vicinity connection on $NCT_A(X)$, The idea of a neutrosophic crisp triple set can also be generalized to the ideas, theories and concepts.

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